

**PECULIARITIES OF THE SELECTED TEACHING METHODS IN
MATHEMATICS**

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Annotation: In this article modern ways of teaching mathematics and its special features were discussed. On the other hand, the basic aim of mathematics education and close connection of creativity with methods of teaching mathematics were noted.

Key words: *problem solving approaches, optimal didactic solutions, subject competences, collaboration , responsibility, Modern teaching requires, situation-based learning, mental activity.*

The teaching and learning of mathematics have always been a major concern in education. Various commissions and committees have laid great emphasis on raising the quality of, instruction in mathematics. The National Policy of Education lays down the importance of mathematics as a vehicle for developing creativity. Recent researches in the area of learning have led to a deeper understanding of "how pupils learn". As a result a broad range of new approaches to the teaching of mathematics have been suggested to achieve optimal learning. The highly structured nature of mathematics, its language and methods of proof have also attracted the attention of psychologists and educationists. Consequently, the old methods of mathematics teaching which

relied heavily upon rote learning and drill have been replaced by methods which rely upon discovery and problem solving approaches[1]. Teaching Mathematics is taking place in rapidly changing conditions. It is necessary to look for optimal didactic and educational solutions encompassing goals and contents as well as forms and teaching methods allowing for preparing students to face the challenges of the contemporary world.

The most significant role of educational system in terms of teaching Mathematics is developing and promoting subject competences as an important factor fostering student's personal development and the development of society. Well organised mathematical and natural sciences education facilitates logical thinking and expressing ideas, organizing own work, planning and organizing the learning process, collaboration and responsibility; it prepares for life in a modern world and enables to perform many jobs. The teacher is required to pay more attention to students' awareness of developing learning skills and study habits, recognizing and analysing problems and predicting solutions to them. Undeniably, the implementation of modern teaching methods and techniques enhances students' curiosity about Mathematics increases their understanding of the basis of mathematical and scientific knowledge. In accordance with the trends teaching Mathematics is supposed to help students understand and solve everyday problems.

Modern teaching requires transition from teacher's subjectivity to that of a student. Transmitting subject knowledge, teachers provide students with creative and critical thinking skills, which consequently let them develop the skill of self-development. Teacher's role is to enhance students' knowledge and skills acquisition in new situations. The process of learning and self-improvement should rely on students' understanding the structure, functions and integration of the brain, sensory preferences, differences in functioning brain hemispheres, brain dominance profiles, learning styles, coping with stress, and the different types of

memory. As far as new educational solutions are concerned, learning strategies facilitating the acquisition of students' knowledge by means of solving theoretical and practical problems are brought to the fore[2]. They comprise practical and intellectual actions as well as the ones that facilitate emotional development, i.e. learning by doing (situation-based learning), learning by communicating (problem-based learning) and experiential learning (simulations, creative thinking techniques, techniques facilitating critical thinking and asking questions).

In this strategy scientific thinking, scientific reasoning and scientific competences of learners play a crucial role. Scientific thinking is an ability of applying scientific knowledge to identify and solve problems as well as drawing conclusions based on empirical observations of nature and society. Scientific reasoning refers to understanding characteristic scientific procedures (a sort of mental activity), methods and tools thanks to which scientific research is conducted and conclusions are drawn, e.g. distinguishing between information based on facts or scientific evidence and information including opinions or assumptions. Induction (inferring general conclusions on the basis of observations) and deduction (inferring the specific from the general) constitute the starting point for reasoning. Scientific competences refer to abilities and willingness to employ knowledge and methodology for explaining phenomena in order to formulate questions and draw evidence-based conclusions.

Action teaching. The overall aim of this method is to gain operational knowledge by a student through a well-planned set of actions. Students construct their knowledge integrating it with materials and various tasks through the prism of their experience. Action teaching is a strategy of a teaching-learning process rooted in Piaget's theory of cognitive development, applied mainly in teaching Mathematics. It aims at gaining operational knowledge not merely by means of chaotic attempts of solving mathematical problems, but via pre-planned by a teacher student's actions. The tasks shall be selected in such a way that enables

students' transition from concrete operations, through symbolic to abstract ones. A thorough analysis of operations within concepts, which must be acquired by students, is the starting point for planning and selecting tasks. Thus, as the designer and promoter of this strategy in Poland – Zofia Krygowska claims, there are two basic teaching principles that the teacher is required to implement:

1. By means of a analysis extracting from a subject matter basic operations within each definition, theorem and proof.
2. Creating problem situations that enhance interiorization and student's mathematical thinking as a specific and conscious use of gradually adopted operations.

Moreover, the consistent application of didactic processes aims at ensuring the accuracy and effectiveness of this process. While developing the understanding of concepts, it is necessary to plan the didactic process properly, so that enactive representations will result from specific actions, iconic representations will stem from symbolic operations and symbolic representations will derive from abstract operations. Interesting teaching methods are proposed to be used in the learning process of mathematics: entertaining mathematics, historical information, computer animation, Japanese origami, and other materials for an accessible and interesting presentation: mathematical sentences, problems, formulas in the process of teaching mathematics, as well as deepen understanding, develop logical and critical thinking, increase student observation and interest in learning mathematics. Entertaining methods of teaching mathematics are used in the professional training of future mathematics teachers in pedagogical universities, teaching mathematics in secondary schools and in preparing children for school. At the same time, entertaining materials are used in the educational process, activating the logical and critical thinking of students and forming the ability to study mathematics. A great role in the selection of means, methods and techniques of work in the lesson is assigned to the teacher. The success of the case

here largely depends on how deeply the teacher penetrates into the specifics of the educational material, how skillfully he sets educational cognitive tasks, taking into account the level of general and mathematical training of students, their personal qualities and predicting the results of using a particular means, method or technique. When choosing the means, methods and techniques of teaching, it must be remembered that they cannot be universalized. None of the means, none of the methods, taken in isolation, will be able to achieve the learning goals.

The chief aim of mathematics education extends beyond motivating students to learn the basic mathematics that they will need in school; rather, it is to convince them (in the hope that they will continue to learn beyond the classroom) to adapt to the mathematical challenges that their future lives will present [3]. Mathematics, as an academic course and as a mode of thought, begins in students' primary education and continues throughout their lifetime learning; moreover, there is a strong relationship between mathematical success and academic success in other courses. Changes and adaptations in other disciplines deeply affect the teaching-learning process in mathematics. Teachers' preferences and opinions regarding pedagogical techniques in mathematics courses are important, because they may reveal their ability to address the needs of students at different learning levels. The study began with a self-evaluation of the teachers' strengths and weaknesses regarding their teaching preferences. As teachers develop their teaching skills, they may help students integrate their mathematical knowledge with other activities, and find out what works best for their personalities and curriculum.

The specificity of the very subject "mathematics" is such that the main thing in teaching is visual-verbal means in various combinations[4]. A mathematics lesson is characterized by the complex use of visual and technical teaching aids. Mathematics, as an academic discipline, has a number of specific features that have influenced the development of teaching methods. The

specificity of mathematics lies in the fact that it is interconnected with other sciences, which influence not only its development as a discipline, but also teaching methods. The methods of other sciences, successfully used by teachers in other areas, are adapted for teaching children mathematics and show high results as a result of their implementation.

To sum up all given facts above, it should be noted that classification of methods of teaching mathematics on the basis of its specificity and interrelation with other sciences: General didactic methods or methods of pedagogy are aimed at studying general didactic laws of teaching mathematics. This includes methods of organizing a lesson, stimulating students to learn, monitoring the educational and cognitive activities of students. Methods of psychology - study the patterns of thought processes in students (analysis, synthesis, generalization, systematization, classification, etc.), on the basis of which the activity approach to the learning process is determined. Logic methods - aimed at studying the forms and laws of logical thinking in students. For example, methods of studying concepts and theorems, methods of induction, deduction and analogy. Methods of mathematics - basic and special methods of cognition, adapted for teaching mathematics. For example, methods of mathematical modeling, learning through problems, the axiomatic method, etc.

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